

Synthesis and characterization of dye based coloured copolyesters

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This article describes the synthesis of four new coloured copolyesters from various phenolphthalein type of dyes like – phenol succinine, resorcinol succinine, pyrogallol succinine and β -naphthol succinine with terephthaloyl chloride in 1,2-dichloroethane. The polymerization was carried out by interfacial polymerization technique. The polymers were characterized by solubility studies, and FTIR spectra. The thermal transition temperatures were determined from DSC thermograms. The surface morphology of these copolyesters was investigated by scanning electron microscopic studies. The resulting polymers were soluble in polar aprotic solvents like DMSO and DMF etc.

In the last few decades a large number of dyes have been used for the synthesis of coloured polymers, which are either inherently coloured or internally coloured polymers. It has been reported in literature that many polymers have been synthesized by interfacial polycondensation technique like – polycarbonates, aliphatic polyamide, aromatic-aliphatic polyamide, polyurea, polyurethane, polysulphonamide, polythioester, polyurethane¹ etc. In the present study, attempts have been made to synthesize four different phenolphthalein type of dyes from four different phenols like – phenol, resorcinol, pyrogallol and β -naphthol with succinic acid. These dyes are then used in the synthesis of four different polymers which are coloured one, along with their characterization are reported.

Results and discussion

(a) Synthesis and characterization of dyes :

All the four dyes prepared by condensation reaction with the loss of H₂O molecule, were coloured amorphous powder, soluble in hot alcohol and sodium hydroxide. Since the structure of these type of dyes were already established by earlier workers², so just for confirmation, the elemental analysis and FT-IR spectroscopic studies have been carried out. All these dyes have shown colour change in alkaline

and acidic medium. The elemental analysis of dyes (Table 1) agrees well with the theoretical value of the chemical structure.

FTIR analysis : All the four dyes (Fig. 1) have shown following characteristic absorption bands² (cm⁻¹) (Ar. O–H str.) 3301, 3188, 3200, 3327, (Ar. =C–H str.) 3122–3030; (C=C ring str.) 1625–1450, (methylene C–H str.) 2950 \pm 20 (asym), 2830 \pm 15 (sym); lactone (C=O str.) 1714–1703, (C–O str.) 1250–1218; (O–H in-plane bending) 1450–1347; (O–H out-of-plane bending) 758–623; (=C–H out-of-plane bending) 860–800. In addition to all these bands, dye – IB and IC have shown aromatic etheral C–O stretching band near 1250–1150 cm⁻¹. All these supports the structure of dye.

(b) Synthesis and characterization of polymers :

In the present work, we report the synthesis of four new polymers which are basically copolyesters and their characterization. All the four polymers were sparingly soluble in common organic solvents. They were also insoluble in mixture of solvents like – mixture of (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane and 1,2-dichloroethane) and (1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane and phenol). All of them were completely soluble in DMSO and DMF at room temperature.

Table 1. Data on yield, colour, molecular formula, molecular weight and elemental analysis of individual dyes

Dye code	Yield (%)	Colour	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Elemental analysis (%)			
					Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Calcd.	Expt.	Calcd.	Expt.
D-IA	55	Dark brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄	270.112	71.08	71.15	5.22	5.17
D-IB	62	Reddish brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₅	284.096	67.58	67.48	4.25	4.31
D-IC	52	Black	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₇	316.096	60.74	60.63	3.83	3.78
D-ID	50	Black	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₄	370.144	77.81	77.85	4.90	4.95

Table 2. Data on reactants used, colour, stirring time and yield of polymers

Polymer code	Dye (g)	Terephthaloyl chloride (g)	NaOH (g)	Colour	Stirring time (min)	Yield (%)
IA	Phenol-succinine (2.7)	2.03	1.5	Black	90	60
IB	Resorcinol-succinine (2.84)	2.03	1.5	Brick red	20	66
IC	Pyrogallol-succinine (3.16)	2.03	2	Black	90	63.4
ID	β -Naphthol-succinine (3.8)	3.1	2.5	Black	10	57

FTIR analysis : The FTIR spectra of polymers (Fig. 2) shows all the absorption bands shown by their corresponding dyes from which they were synthesized. The absence of (Ar. O–H str.) have shown the complete esterification of dyes, except dye – IC having pyrogallol moiety (Ar, O–H str.) 3100 cm^{-1} . All the polymers have shown (C–O str.) of ester as well as lactone ring near $1750\text{--}1730\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The strong absorbance at $1340\text{--}1280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C–O str. vibration) further supports the presence of ester group as well as lactone ring in polymer structure. The (O=C=C (asy) str.) near $1168\text{--}1140\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were indicative of aryl conjugated system.

Table 3. Thermal transition temperatures ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) of polymers

Polymer code	Thermal transition temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)		
	T_g	T_m	T_{cl}
P-IA	–	187.7	343.3
P-IB	74.9	187.6	354.1
P-IC	143.8	203.7	378.3
P-ID	133.9	198.5	359.5

T_g , Glass transition temperature; T_m , mesophase formation temperature; T_{cl} , isotropisation temperature.

Thermal characterization : The thermal transition of polymers (Fig. 3) were investigated by using DSC and capillary melting point apparatus. Melting was not observed for these polymers in a capillary melting tube under normal conditions.

Noel *et al.*³ used DSC to study liquid crystalline thermotropic polyesters with a terphenyl mesogen in the polymer chain. In the present case, the dye moiety with alternate phenyl ring in the polymeric chain acts as mesogen while ester group acts as spacer. As the aliphatic carbon chain is present in lactone ring of polymer, so the value of thermal transition temperature (given in Table 3) may be considerably less than that of the wholly aromatic polyesters or polyesters from phenolphthalein and fluorescein. The T_g values are in the range $74.9\text{--}143.9^{\circ}\text{C}$ except P-IA having no T_g value. The T_g of polymers depends on many factors like molecular weight, tacticity, chemical structure, polarity etc. The T_g values of these polymers are in the order $\text{P-IC} > \text{P-ID} > \text{P-IB}$. As all these polymers have bulky three-dimensional dye moiety, which is believed to stiffen the polymeric chain segment, this creates more hindrance in the internal rotations of C–C within the backbone of polymeric chain and

Fig. 1. FT-IR Spectrum of dyes - D-IA, D-IB, D-IC, D-ID and terephthaloyl chloride (TPHC).

raise temperature required for segmental motion. The closed ring structure of P-IC with symmetrically attached -OH group at two different benzene ring is the main cause for highest T_g value among these polymers, but in the P-IB, low T_g value may be due to either formation of low molecular weight polymer or some different tacticity as compared to P-IC. The P-ID having condensed ring pattern (naphthalene moiety) also provides much rigidity to the polymeric backbone and results in high T_g value.

By visual observation, during action of heat on these polymers under normal condition, melting was not observed. All these polymers were started to change colour from original around $180\text{--}200^{\circ}\text{C}$ with some needle like structure formation in texture, it supports that, some phase-transformation within the polymeric structure occurs corre-

Fig. 2. FT-IR Spectrum of polymers - P-1A, P-1B, P-1C and P-1D.

Fig. 3. DSC Thermogram of polymers - P-1A, P-1B, P-1C and P-1D.

Fig. 4. SEM Micrographs of polymers - P-1A, P-1B, P-1C and P-1D.

sponding to the endothermic peak in the temperature range 187.6–203.7°C (i.e. T_m , mesophase formation temperature). The isotropisation temperature (T_{ci}) are in the range 343.3–378°C. As the nature of peak in thermogram is endothermic, it reflects the amorphous liquid – crystalline behaviour of polymer.

Scanning electron microscopy: SEM micrographs presents the three-dimensional surface morphology of polymeric network (Fig. 4). The micrograph of P-1A (Fig. 4(a)) shows a granular structure having cavities, which may be due to entrapped water molecule or solvent. Fig. 4(b) shows the almost homogenous fibrillar structure with small ridges like growth on the surface. Figs. 4(c) and (d) shows mosaic structure. More number of dense particles are aggregated at one place and forms the crystalline appearance, which reflects the good bonding strength of this polymer. Figs. 4(e) and (f) shows granular structure and reflects the toughness of the surface.

Experimental

Elemental analysis of dyes were carried out on Carlo ERBA-EA-1108 elemental analyzer; FTIR spectra on Shimadzu FTIR 8201 PC by incorporating the dye and polymer in DRS (Diffused Reflection Spectroscopic) mode and terephthaloyl chloride in KBr pellet. DSC thermogram

Scheme 1. The reaction of synthesis of dyes.

were recorded on Seiko Instrument (Japan)-Insta 220^o (range : 100^o to +600^oC) differential scanning calorimeter at a heating rate of 10^oC/min in N₂ atmosphere and SEM on Leica stereoscan 440 SEM with Phoenix EDAX EDXS.

Succinic acid and NaOH (NICE), phenol, 1,2-dichloroethane (s.d. fine chem. Ltd.), pyrogallol, n-heptane, (CDH), resorcinol (Merck), β-naphthol (Ranbaxy) used were of A.R. grade. 1,2-Dichloroethane and n-heptane were distilled before use and remaining used as received.

(a) *Synthesis of dyes (monomers)* : All the four dyes were prepared as below :

Succinic acid (1 mol) and any of phenol like phenol, resorcinol, pyrogallol or β-naphthol (2 mol) were condensed in presence of few drops of conc. H₂SO₄ at 150–170^oC in an oil bath for about 6–10 h depending upon the phenol used. The solidified mass of crude dye obtained on cooling was purified by dissolving it in dil. NaOH and reprecipitated by dil. HCl, filtered, washed with H₂O and ethanol and dried for 2 h (represented in Scheme 1).

(b) *Synthesis of polymers* :

All the polymers were prepared by stirred interfacial polycondensation technique. The respective dye and NaOH

Scheme 2. The reaction for synthesis of polymers.

were dissolved in 250 ml distilled water, filtered, and kept in jar of Waring blender (covered with heavy duty aluminium foil pierced at the center to place a powder funnel to introduce reagents) and stirred with high speed. A solution of terephthaloyl chloride was prepared in 40 ml distilled 1,2-dichloromethane and poured into the dye solution as quickly as possible. The mixture was stirred for 10–90 min. The faded colour of dye and increase in viscosity of the solution was the indicative of the progress of the reaction. After discontinuation of stirring, 50 ml of n-heptane was added to remove some of the 1,2-dichloroethane and stirred slowly for 7–8 min, filtered, washed with water and dried. The details of reactant, stirring time and yield are given in Table 2 and polymer synthesis is represented in Scheme 2.

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